

No-debt Movement in US Evangelicalism

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Entry tags: Evangelical religion, Protestantism, Religious Group, Religious Practice, American Christianity, Evangelicalism

Financial crises and economic recessions over the past few decades have given rise to the no-debt movement in both religious and non-religious spaces. Many evangelicals in the United States, in particular, have embraced the no-debt movement that emphasizes debt elimination, financial stewardship, and generosity. Financial ministries such as Crown Financial Ministries and Dave Ramsey Solutions have become an integral part of the religious landscape as they provide resources, seminars, and curriculum to churches to help congregants get out of debt and generate wealth. The leaders of these ministries, in addition to pastors and church leaders, work to weave theology into financial practices to help adherents view debt through a theological lens. The no-debt movement is not only evangelical in its theology but also reflects American values and culture of freedom and agency. Although there has also been an increase of non-religious no-debt organizations and leaders who promote similar practices as evangelical no-debt leaders, the evangelical no-debt movement adds a theological lens into the American financial experience that provides adherents with new language and new practices. Debt is viewed as a form of slavery and adherents of the no-debt movement use various biblical texts to support their position. The only appropriate response to debt is to attack it until it is gone. This means that many people in the no-debt movement adjust their financial lifestyles in order to aggressively pay off debt. In addition to the aversion of debt, the evangelical no-debt movement promotes the concept of stewardship and generosity. Stewardship is the belief that God created everything and things like money, assets, and wealth belong to God, not the person. God entrusts people to manage assets like money and they are responsible for stewarding God's money well. Excessive consumer debt is a sign that a person has not been a good steward of what God has given them and thus they need to make changes in their thinking and actions in order to get in line with God's way of handling finances. Once a person is out of debt they are able to become more effective stewards of God's provision because they can now be generous with what God has given them. Many adherents of the no-debt movement promote generosity as one of the ultimate goals of financial freedom. God give people money and wealth so they can steward it well and give it away to people in need.

Date Range: 1980 CE - 2022 CE

Region: United States (all 50 states)

Region tags: North America, United States of America, United States, Lower 48

The United States of America

Status of Participants:

✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Ramsey, Dave. *Dave Ramsey's Complete Guide to Money*. Brentwood: Lampo Press, 2011.
- Source 2: Ramsey, Dave. *The Total Money Makeover: A Proven Plan for Financial Fitness*. Nashville:

Thomas Nelson, 2007.

– Source 3: Alcorn, Randy. *Managing God's Money*. Carol Stream: Tyndale, 2011.

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

Online sources for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: <https://www.ramseysolutions.com/>

– Source 1 Description: This is the homepage for Dave Ramsey's Financial Peace University and provides information about all the programs and products available to the public.

– Source 2 URL: <https://www.crown.org/>

– Source 2 Description: This is the homepage for Crown Financial Ministries. This site provides information about the programs and products available to the public.

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

– Source 1 URL: <https://www.crown.org/>

– Source 1 Description: Crown Financial Ministries is one of the most influential and popular ministries in the no-debt movement.

– Source 2 URL: <https://www.ramseysolutions.com/>

– Source 2 Description: Ramsey Solutions is arguably the most popular no-debt organization in the US terms of users

– Source 3 URL: <https://gatewaypeople.com/resources/stewardship>

– Source 3 Description: Gateway Church in Southlake, TX is one of the most visible and popular church in America that promote no-debt ideology

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

Is the cultural contact competitive:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

Notes: Although most adherents taking a seminar from Crown Financial Ministries or Ramsey Solutions identify as evangelical, not all participants are evangelical. Some non-evangelicals are invited to attend seminars from their evangelical friends, family, or acquaintances. Non-Christian or non-evangelicals who take Dave Ramsey's seminars have claimed that although the Bible is referenced, there is no pressure to convert to evangelicalism during the seminars.

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

Is the cultural contact neutral:

– No

Notes: The no-debt movement views itself as a challenge to the consumer debt culture in the United States. Consumer debt culture is not neutral and neither is the no-debt movement.

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– Yes

Notes: Crown Financial Ministries states that they use their financial stewardship curriculum as a means of spreading the Gospel of Jesus Christ. Those who identify in the no-debt movement and who use Crown's materials are actively encouraged to proselytize. Those who follow other no-debt leaders like Dave Ramsey are not actively encouraged to evangelize. However, many churches use Financial Peace University from Dave Ramsey as a way to get unchurched people to attend services and classes at their church campuses. Here is a video from Crown Financial Ministries outlining their redemptive stewardship theology - <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=d7wBC6VluDU>

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

Is proselytizing mandated for religious professionals:

– Yes

Notes: No-debt adherents who also identify as evangelical believe that it is the responsibility of pastors, leaders, and lay people to share the Gospel and convert non-believers.

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for all adherents:

– Yes

Notes: Evangelicals in the no-debt movement believe that it is their charge and calling to participate in the Great Commission and participate in evangelism.

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Is missionary work mandated for religious professionals:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Is missionary work mandated for all adherents:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Is proselytization coercive:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

Does the religion have official political support

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

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↳ Are apostates prosecuted or punished:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 33000000

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Estimated population, percentage of sample region: 33

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

Notes: Evangelical no-debt adherents believe that the Protestant Bible is the literal Word of God. Most of them believe in some form of plenary verbal inspiration and articulate beliefs that the Bible must be taken literally in all aspects. In regards to finances, many pastors and preachers declare that the Bible references issues with money more than sex, heaven, and hell. You can see a teaching on this at this link from John Piper - <https://www.desiringgod.org/messages/free-from-money-rich-toward-god>

Reference: Millard J. Erickson. Christian Theology. Baker Academic. isbn: 9780801021824.

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

Notes: Financial ministries that promote no-debt philosophies use the Protestant Bible as their primary authoritative text. They use passages such as Proverbs 22:7 which says "The rich rule over the poor, and the borrower is the slave to the lender."

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Are they oral:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Revealed by a high god:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Inspired by high god:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Originated from non-divine human being:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

Is iconography present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

– At home

– Some public spaces

Notes: One unique form of iconography in the no-debt movement is the preservation and presentation of cut-up credit cards. There are churches that complete no-debt education in the form of Dave Ramsey's Financial Peace University or Crown Financial Ministries where they hold credit card cutting rituals. Adherents cut up their credit cards and then place the pieces into shadow boxes or clear Christmas ornaments as a way of showing devotion to the curriculum/instructor/church and also as a reminder that they cannot use those cards again.

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Eyes (stylized or not):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Portrayals of afterlife:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Humans:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Other features of iconography:

– Yes

Notes: The iconography of making artwork out of cut-up credit cards reflects American values of freedom and agency. They are reminders of a broken past (in terms of financial spending) and a redemptive future.

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

Notes: One specific site is the Dave Ramsey main office in Franklin, Tennessee. People travel from all over the country to visit the office and perform their debt-free scream in person. The debt-free scream is performed when a family or individual has paid off all of their debt and are now debt-free.

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

Notes: People travel from all over the country to visit the offices of Dave Ramsey. One of the primary reasons people travel to the office complex is to perform the debt-free scream.

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

Notes: Most people who follow Crown Financial Ministries or Ramsey Solutions adhere to some form of evangelical theology. They believe in the anthropology of mind, body, and spirit.

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: Most participants in no-debt ministries adhere to an evangelical view of the afterlife where people who accept Jesus Christ as their Lord and Savior live with God for eternity and those who do not live apart from God in eternity.

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

Are grave goods present:

– No

Notes: Pastors who teach people to stay out of debt usually focus on consumerism. They explain to their congregants that they rarely or never hear people on their deathbed talk about what they wish

they would have purchased. One pastor used to say, "There are no U-Hauls to Heaven." This meant that a person cannot take their stuff with them when they die. The purpose of these statements from various pastors is to encourage evangelicals to not focus on material goods. The reason people are in debt is often that they live beyond their financial means in order to have material goods they cannot afford. Here is a teaching from a pastor on this subject - <http://www.gracenorco.org/messages/management/>

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

As cenotaphs:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

In cemetery:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

Family tomb-crypt:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

Other formal burial type:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– Yes

Notes: Although God has no physical form, the Bible often describes attributes or actions of God in anthropomorphic terms.

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– Yes

Notes: Ministries that focus on no-debt within evangelicalism believe that God is unquestionably good. They argue that believing that God is good is beyond mere intellectual belief but it is lived out by a person's actions. See: <https://www.ramseysolutions.com/personal-growth/how-to-trust-god>

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:

– Yes [specify]: God is interested in personal finance according to those who adhere to the no-debt movement. There are numerous scriptures that are used to support the theology that God wants people to be good stewards of their finances.

Notes: Without biblical scriptural support, there would be very little support amongst evangelicals in regards to viewing debt as evil. However, there are numerous scriptures that are cited in support of the movement. Here is a link that provides a helpful overview of the rationale: <https://www.ramseysolutions.com/personal-growth/managing-money-gods-way>

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

Notes: God knows all in both the heavenly and earthly realms.

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

Notes: Scriptural support for this concept comes from Proverbs 21:2, Jeremiah 17:10, 1 Samuel 16:7, Romans 8:17, Acts 15:8. Since God knows the hearts of man and man is sinful and evil in their fallen state, they need God's direction and transformative power in all aspects of their lives including finances. Pastor Robert Morris at Gateway Church in Southlake, TX wrote the book called *The Blessed Life*. He contends that people need to be transformed from their selfish ways to being generous in all areas of their lives including finances. God knows the selfish desires of peoples' hearts and it is up to each individual to allow God to transform their hearts and minds towards a biblical perspective of generosity.

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

Notes: God knows the hearts of people. Scriptural support for this concept comes from Proverbs 21:2, Jeremiah 17:10, 1 Samuel 16:7, Romans 8:17, Acts 15:8.

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

Notes: There is a spectrum of beliefs within evangelicalism regarding predestination and free will. Financial ministries and leaders within the no-debt movement often strike a middle ground. Dave Ramsey was quoted in 2009 as saying, "Pray like it all depends on God...but work like it all depends on you." This statement reflects the idea that although God may or may not know what is going to happen with an individual (especially in terms of their financial situation), it is necessary for human agents to act and make proper choices with their finances.

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:

– Yes [specify]: God knows the world better than humans. The Book of Job highlights this reality where God asks Job where he was when God laid the foundations of the world and marked off its dimensions (Job 38:4-7).

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

The supreme high god can reward:

– Yes

Notes: The no-debt movement is rooted in the language of blessed rather than reward. Generosity leads to blessings but not as a direct one-to-one transaction. God blesses people so they can be a blessing to others. Yes, God can reward but the no-debt movement differentiates their theology and practice from the Word of Faith and Prosperity Gospel movements. See this teaching from Robert Morris on generosity and blessings: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Cb8if9nRjgM>

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

The supreme high god can punish:

– Yes

Notes: God can punish but much of the no-debt theology focuses on the depravity of humanity and the consequences of their evil actions rather than divine punishment. Dave Ramsey argues that poverty in America is not judgment but is a result of poor actions.

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– No

Notes: God has direct causal efficacy and there is nothing believed to be accidental or arbitrary in terms of God's actions.

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:

– Yes

Notes: Within evangelical theology, God is viewed as demonstrating attributes such as love, kindness, graciousness, and forgiveness (Exodus 34:6-7).

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:

– Yes

Notes: God is a jealous God who also brings down judgment on those who do not live for Him (Exodus 34:14).

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:

– No

Notes: An important biblical text regarding not worshipping money is Matthew 6:24 which says, "No one can serve two masters; for either he will hate the one and love the other, or he will be devoted to one and despise the other. You cannot serve God and wealth." The word wealth is Mammon in Greek. Leaders and advocates of the no-debt movement in evangelicalism contend that wealth or Mammon is a false god. Within the American context, Mammon is viewed as being self-serving and evil. Yet, there is a distinction between wealth and the love of wealth. In 2019, Dave Ramsey stated, "The Bible does NOT say "Money is the root of all evil" It says "The LOVE of money is..." We are called to manage money for God, not worship it." Being in debt is worshipping money since it forces the debtor to focus on money rather than generosity.

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

Notes: God speaks to people through the Bible, the Holy Spirit, and prophecy. There is a spectrum of views concerning how God speaks to people but there is

a consensus that God does speak to people.

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ In trance possession:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Through divination practices:

– Yes

Notes: Evangelicals look to biblical scriptures such as Deuteronomy 18:10-11 and 1 Samuel 28 to argue that God is against divination.

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

Notes: All believers in Jesus are considered priests and thus can communicate directly with God. See 1 Peter 2:9

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Only through monarch

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Other form of communication with living:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– Yes

Notes: Angels, cherubim, seriphim, demons, and the devil are supernatural beings that can be seen.

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– Yes

Notes: Evil supernatural beings such as demons or the devil can be felt and can influence the actions and decisions of people.

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Non-human supernatural beings knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ These supernatural beings can reward:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ These supernatural beings can punish:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

Notes: Evangelicals believe that angels rejoice when sinners repent and get saved by accepting Jesus Christ as their Lord and Savior. They base this belief on Luke 15:10

which says, "In the same way, I tell you, there is rejoicing in the presence of the angels of God over one sinner who repents."

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Organized hierarchically:

– Yes

Notes: Spiritual beings have a hierarchy. The Triune God (Father, Son, and Holy Spirit) is at the top of the hierarchy with Satan, demons, and angels below.

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:

– Yes

Notes: God rules and reigns over the realms of heaven and earth. Satan and demons have influence over the earth and can influence the actions of humans. Crown Financial Ministries released an evangelical devotional for people to read and reflect on different biblical scriptures and journal about their reflections. Part of the devotional explains the importance of not holding onto anger because it may give the devil an opportunity to influence their life. See the devotional below.

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Other organization for pantheon:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously "moral" or "ethical" norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

Notes: Adherents of no-debt theology believe that they have a moral responsibility to pay all debts and to be debt-free. They believe that people must commit themselves to God as they pursue debt elimination. When describing his journey out of debt, Pastor Robert Morris of Gateway Church in Southlake, TX explained, "We [Morris and his wife, Debbie] bought nothing during that time because we had made a solemn commitment to get out of debt—no matter

how long it took. We said to the Lord, we are serious about this, and we showed it." God is watching those who are in debt to see if they honor their commitment to not only getting out of debt but also whether they should pay all of their debt off without it going to a settlement or using debt relief. However, what happens when debt mounts up and people cannot pay it? Dave Ramsey contends that it is acceptable to only pay a portion of the debt if a person is broke. If a person has the means to pay the debt, they need to pay it. If they do not have the means, they should pay what they can if a settlement can be reached. Robert Morris - <https://gatewaypublishing.com/blogs/articles/get-out-of-debt> Dave Ramsey on the morality of settling debt - <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ZeQcHAHx0e0>

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

– Yes

Notes: Evangelicals believe God is against murder according to numerous passages in the Bible. When it comes to financial freedom and not living in debt, some pastors make interpretive connections between murder and living on a budget. Pastor Robert Morris from Gateway Church in Southlake, TX gave a sermon in 2019 called The Financial Ten Commandments. He presented correlations between finances and the Ten Commandments from the Book of Exodus. He explained that the sixth commandment of finance is live on a budget and it compares to the sixth commandment, "Do not murder." Morris acknowledges that this is a stretch but he states that when you do not live on a budget, you are killing yourself, and if you are living on a budget, sometimes you want to kill yourself. See the full message on video here: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=chowZo8tgMo>

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:

– Yes

Notes: Murder is not acceptable in any context or form.

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:

– Yes

Notes: Murder is unacceptable in any form.

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Adultery:

– Yes

Notes: God is against adultery according to various verses in the Bible. In 2019, Pastor Robert Morris gave a sermon on the Ten Financial Commandments and compared adultery to living above God's provision for a person's life. Living above one's means financially means they are not content with what they have. People who do this are telling God that they are not content with God and what God has given them. Dave Ramsey has a different view of adultery in terms of right and wrong. It's not just wrong theologically but practically it is wrong because Dave can no longer trust the person. Dave Ramsey has numerous quotes where he explicitly states that adultery is wrong. He explains, "We have a moral code of conduct at our office. I fire people if they have extramarital affairs." Ramsey also writes in his book *EntreLeadership* that he, "won't let a team member stay if they decide to have an affair. If their spouse can't trust them, neither can I." Within the no-debt community, there have been instances where leaders in the no-debt movement have been caught in adultery and other leaders covered it up. Dave Ramsey's organization was in a tough place when one of his most visible leaders, Chris Hogan, had an affair. Ramsey's views on adultery were well documented but Hogan was allowed to remain on as a leader until he resigned in 2021. Ramsey and the board of directors were aware of what was going on with Hogan but continued to use Hogan to promote books and programs within Ramsey Solutions. See <https://julieroys.com/dave-ramsey-board-kept-adulterer-chris-hogan-on-staff/> Ramsey Solutions on Moral Code - <https://www.ramseysolutions.com/business/employees-have-to-follow-the-moral-code> Robert Morris - The Ten Financial Commandments - <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=chowZo8tgMo>

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Incest:

– Yes

Notes: Incest is not permitted by God.

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Other sexual practices:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:

– Yes

Notes: Evangelicals believe that God is against lying and lying is a sin.

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:

– Yes

Notes: Adherents of the no-debt movement are encouraged to pay off their debts as a way to honor Jesus' teaching of "let your 'yes' be 'yes' and your 'no' be 'no'" in Matthew 5:37.

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:

– Yes

Notes: God does not want people to be idle and lazy. Dave Ramsey uses Proverbs 13:4 which says, "The soul of a lazy man desires, and has nothing; But the soul of the diligent shall be made rich." He also likes to quote Proverbs 26:16 which says, "The lazy man is wiser in his own eyes Than seven men who can answer sensibly." These verses are used to support a theology that God does not want people to be lazy and people must work hard to honor God.

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:

– Yes

Notes: Evangelicals believe that God is against sorcery and divination according to Exodus 22:18 and Deuteronomy 18:11-12.

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:

– Yes

Notes: Evangelicals often quote Matthew 5:38-39 where Jesus says that people are to turn the other cheek in terms of discouraging non-lethal violence.

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:

– Yes

Notes: No-debt adherents believe that God wants people to be wise and not take unnecessary risks, particularly financially. They need to be good stewards of what God gives them because all things belong to God.

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:

– Yes

Notes: Evangelicals desire to support and respect elders in the community. They use biblical passages like Leviticus 19:32 which says "Stand up in the presence of the aged, show respect for the elderly and revere your God. I am the LORD."

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:

– Yes

Notes: Evangelicals use biblical passages such as Ephesians 4:29, James 1:26, and Proverbs 11:13 to support the belief that God does not want people to gossip.

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:

– Yes

Notes: Since all things on earth belong to God, property crimes are a violation of God and reflect a lack of proper stewardship.

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:

– Yes

Notes: Although most evangelicals contend that they are no longer obligated to observe any ritual laws of the Old Testament, there are some unique ritual observances that are important to the no-debt movement. A key ritual is the giving of an offering or tithe. Crown Financial Ministries, Dave Ramsey, Pastor Robert Morris, and numerous other leaders teach that all followers of Jesus need to be tithing regularly. It is considered an act of worship and needs to be done regularly. When people tithe, they are declaring that their finances and assets belong

to God and they are demonstrating proper stewardship.

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:

– Yes

Notes: Although most evangelicals contend that they are no longer obligated to observe any ritual laws of the Old Testament, there are some unique ritual observances that are important to the no-debt movement. A key ritual is the giving of an offering or tithe. Crown Financial Ministries, Dave Ramsey, Pastor Robert Morris, and numerous other leaders teach that all followers of Jesus need to be tithing regularly. It is considered an act of worship and needs to be done regularly. When people tithe, they are declaring that their finances and assets belong to God and they are demonstrating proper stewardship.

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:

– Yes

Notes: Evangelicals believe that God wants all people to be saved (1 Timothy 2:4). God uses various methods to connect with people and many people in the no-debt movement believe that a Bible-based financial curriculum can reach people who might not regularly attend church. Watch the video of a person giving a testimony of how they found Jesus while taking Financial Peace University - <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=nfsZgCsk-OY>

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:

– Yes

Notes: Adherents of the evangelical no-debt movement hold to a broad spectrum of beliefs regarding economic fairness. Some adherents strongly believe in economic fairness for all and that God mandates his followers to carry out economic justice and equity. Others believe that poverty is a result of poor individual choices and has no connection to economic or socio-cultural factors. God wants people to work and it is up to each individual to become economically stable and generate wealth.

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

Notes: Eschatologically, evangelicals believe that God will mete out punishment for those who reject him. It is an individual choice and those who reject God's gift of salvation through the death and resurrection of Jesus Christ will live eternally apart from God. See a video sermon of Robert Morris sharing about eternal life - <https://gatewaypeople.com/series/revealing-the-mystery?sermon=the-beginning-of-the-ministry>

Reference: George Eldon Ladd. *A Theology of the New Testament*. Wm. B. Eerdmans Publishing. isbn: 9780802806802.

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Done only by high god:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Done by other entities or through other means [specify]

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Done randomly:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Other [specify]

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Supernatural punishments in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Other [specify]

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

Notes: Within the no-debt movement, there is a belief that God blesses those who are good stewards of what God has given people. This is different from the Word of Faith movement in some neo-charismatic circles that focus more on giving to receive more blessings from God. The no-debt movement places a greater emphasis on individual agency and that a person is supposed to align themselves with God's purposes of stewardship.

Reference: Gunnar Johnson. *Generous Life Journey*. Charisma Media. isbn: 9781629986999.

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Done only by high god:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Done randomly:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: Many evangelicals believe that God will provide rewards and treasures to those who are faithful to him in this life. Evangelicals talk about different crowns they can receive for their faithful life in Jesus Christ. See a list of the crowns here - <https://davidjeremiah.blog/what-kind-of-rewards-will-believers-receive-in-heaven/>

Reference: Dr. David Jeremiah. The Jeremiah Study Bible, NIV. Worthy Books. isbn: 9781683973041.

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Supernatural rewards in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– Yes

Notes: Most no-debt evangelicals believe in the end times and the afterlife in eternity. They hold to a literal reading of the Book of Revelation where believers will live with God for eternity and there will be no more pain, tears, suffering, or death.

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of eternal happiness:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as a superior life form:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in a superior realm:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Other [specify]

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: For evangelical no-debt adherents, it is not so much about rewards rather than it is about receiving God's blessings. Financial blessings from God are not to be held on to but are to be given away to bless other people.

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:

– No

Notes: No-debt leaders like Dave Ramsey share that it is not political success or politics that influences a person's financial and economic status. Rather it is determined by individual choices. However, Ramsey and many other leaders also identify as conservative on the political spectrum and hold fiscal and socially conservative political positions. See Dave Ramsey's interview on CNN regarding the 2016 election and the economy - <https://www.cnn.com/videos/tv/2015/09/05/exp-dave-ramsey-on-2016-race.cnn>

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

- ↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:
– Yes
Notes: Evangelicals pray for traveling mercies. Here are some examples of traveling mercy prayers: <https://www.ryanhart.org/prayers-for-traveling-mercies/>
Specific to this answer:
Region: USA
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:
– No
Specific to this answer:
Region: USA
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:
– No
Specific to this answer:
Region: USA
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:
– No
Specific to this answer:
Region: USA
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:
– No
Specific to this answer:
Region: USA
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:
– No
Specific to this answer:
Region: USA
- ↳ Other [specify]
– No
Specific to this answer:
Region: USA

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– Yes

Notes: Evangelicals believe that Jesus Christ is the Messiah or Anointed One who fulfills God's plan of redemption for all creation. The death and resurrection of Jesus Christ allow all people to have a relationship with God. While many other Christian traditions and even some Charismatic traditions emphasize Jesus Christ's messianic Second Coming, some evangelicals (particularly Neo-Charismatics) put a large emphasis on Jesus Christ's messianic role in the present in addition to his second coming.

Reference: George Eldon Ladd. *The Gospel of the Kingdom*. Wm. B. Eerdmans Publishing. isbn: 9780802812803.

Reference: George Eldon Ladd. *A Theology of the New Testament*. Wm. B. Eerdmans Publishing. isbn: 9780802806802.

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

Is the messiah's purpose known:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

Messiah is a political figure who restores political rule:

– Yes

Notes: Many no-debt evangelicals believe that Jesus Christ will return as a king who will fully usher in the Kingdom of God. The Book of Revelation gives depictions of Jesus Christ as a king with a crown, sword, and throne.

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

Messiah is a priestly figure who restores religious traditions:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Other purpose:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

Is an eschatology present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Eschaton in this lifetime:

– Yes

Notes: Although many evangelicals focus on the end times, there are numerous evangelicals that hold to a now and not yet eschatology. This means that many people experience the blessings of salvation now but it is not fully realized until the final resurrection, final judgment, and when God makes all things new.

Reference: George Eldon Ladd. *A Theology of the New Testament*. Wm. B. Eerdmans Publishing. isbn: 9780802806802.

Reference: George Eldon Ladd. *The Gospel of the Kingdom*. Wm. B. Eerdmans Publishing. isbn: 9780802812803.

Reference: George Eldon Ladd. *The Presence of the Future*. Wm. B. Eerdmans Publishing. isbn: 9780802815316.

Reference: George E. Ladd. *The Last Things*. Wipf and Stock Publishers. isbn: 9781592444588.

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Eschaton at specified time in future:

– No

Notes: Evangelicals (no-debt adherents included) adhere to the teaching of Jesus in Matthew 24:35-37 that says no one knows when the end will come.

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in near future:

– Yes

Notes: Evangelicals believe that there the eschaton is imminent even though they do not know the day or time. American evangelicals have a particular fascination with the eschaton and many live with an expectation that it is near.

Reference: Paul Boyer. *When Time Shall Be No More*. Harvard University Press. isbn:

Reference: Paul Boyer. When Time Shall Be No More. Harvard University Press. isbn: 9780674028616.

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in distant future:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Eschaton at some other time:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end:

– Yes

Notes: Some evangelicals believe that voting for the right candidate may trigger the start of the eschaton. See this article - <https://www.newsweek.com/trump-will-bring-about-end-of-world-evangelicals-end-times-779643>

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Divine judgment event:

– Yes

Notes: The eschaton will usher in wars, famine, and tribulation. God will judge all people who have ever lived. Those who do not follow Jesus and accept him as their personal savior will participate in the great white throne judgment. Those who accept Jesus as their personal savior will experience the judgment seat of Christ. For more information - <https://davidjeremiah.blog/what-kind-of-rewards-will-believers-receive-in-heaven/>

Reference: Millard J. Erickson. Christian Theology. Baker Academic. isbn: 9780801021824.

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Restoration of the world:

– Yes

Notes: There is the belief that God will restore heaven and earth and all things will be made new.

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Start of a new temporal cycle:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Establishment of a new political system:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Establishment of a new religious system:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ All religious in-group members will survive the eschaton:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ A subset of religion in-group members will survive the eschaton:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Everyone in the world will survive the eschaton:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Evangelicals (and no-debt adherents) hold to social norms such as financial and material generosity, sexual purity, monogamy, and hospitality are not just practices that make God happy; they are an important part of being in a relationship with God where God can use them to bless others and demonstrate his love for all people.

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

What is the nature of this distinction:

– Present and clear

Notes: Evangelicals adhering to no-debt theology believe that there is a clear distinction between the culture of the "world" and the culture prescribed by the "bible" when it comes to finances and materiality. Americans are taught to be consumers and thus become materialistic to the point where materialism can become its own form of idol worship. To properly follow Jesus, evangelicals must recognize this dichotomy and learn to be stewards of God's finances and material blessings rather than owners and consumers of them.

Reference: Randy Alcorn. *Money, Possessions, and Eternity*. Tyndale House Publishers, Inc.. isbn: 9781414341644.

Reference: Randy Alcorn. *Managing God's Money*. Tyndale House Publishers, Inc.. isbn: 9781414351940.

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Within no-debt teachings and finances, many evangelical leaders use financial moral norms such as Dave Ramsey's seven baby steps or Pastor Robert Morris' Ten Financial Commandments. These lists are used to help people stay within their financial means and to eliminate debt so they can position themselves to be blessed by God and to be a blessing to other people.

Reference: Robert Morris. *The Blessed Life*. Baker Books. isbn: 9781441230614.

Reference: Joseph Singleton. *The Lord's Financial Plan*. BAC Publishers. isbn: 0965573087.

Reference: Dave Ramsey. The Total Money Makeover. Thomas Nelson Inc. isbn: 9781595550781.

Reference: Dave Ramsey. Financial Peace. Lampo. isbn: 9780963571236.

Reference: Dave Ramsey. Dave Ramsey's Complete Guide to Money. Ramsey Press. isbn: 9781937077761.

Reference: Dave Ramsey. Baby Steps Millionaires. Ramsey Press. isbn: 9781942121602.

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Specifically moral norms are implicitly linked to vague metaphysical concepts:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Specifically moral norms are explicitly linked to vague metaphysical entities:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked to impersonal cosmic order (e.g. karma):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked in some way to an anthropomorphic being:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked explicitly to commands of anthropomorphic being:

– Yes

Notes: Evangelicals (and no-debt adherents) follow the teachings of Jesus Christ and interpret them as a roadmap of how to live in both Heaven and earth in the present day. The moral norms that Jesus Christ taught are not just good ideas but should be viewed as the way that adherents can align themselves with God to receive blessings and in turn bless other people.

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Specifically moral norms are have no special connection to metaphysical:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Moral norms apply to:

- All individuals within society
- All individuals within contemporary world
- All individuals (any time period)

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Honesty / trustworthiness / integrity:

– Yes

Notes: Integrity and honesty are of utmost importance within the no-debt movement. It is necessary for people to pay off their debts and to own their mistakes with their finances.

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Courage (in battle):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Courage (generic):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Compassion / empathy / kindness / benevolence:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Mercy / forgiveness / tolerance:

– Yes

Notes: Forgiveness and mercy are core aspects of evangelical practice and theology. Jesus Christ's work on the cross and his resurrection brought about forgiveness of sins for the whole world. Evangelicals are encouraged to forgive others just as Jesus Christ did in the first century. See <https://evangelicalfocus.com/mind-and-heart/1812/forgiving-and-asking-for-forgiveness>

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Generosity / charity:

– Yes

Notes: Adherents of the no-debt movement believe that generosity is one of the primary tenets of financial theology. God gives people material goods and money to bless others and those who follow Jesus must steward their finances well in order to position themselves to bless others who need assistance. Generosity is more than an action or a moral standard. No-debt evangelical leaders teach that generosity is part of your anthropology. These leaders help people come to an understanding that financial generosity is a crucial component of life because people are created to be generous. Those who follow Jesus need to change their wrong perceptions of humanity that depicts people as consumers, not givers. When people understand the Imago Dei and accept the reality that they are supposed to be generous because God is generous, they are able to change their views on money, debt, and consumerism and eradicate financial debt from their lives. See Pastor Robert Morris' teaching on generosity - <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Gb8if9nRjgM>

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Selflessness / selfless giving:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Righteousness / moral rectitude:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Ritual purity / ritual adherence / abstention from sources of impurity:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Respectfulness / courtesy:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Familial obedience / filial piety:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Fidelity / loyalty:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Cooperation:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Independence / creativity / freedom:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Moderation / frugality:

– Yes

Notes: Many no-debt adherents live by Dave Ramsey's quote, "If you will live like no one else, later you can live like no one else." This means that people are to live financially frugal and moderate lives by not spending money on entertainment, vacations, or other goods outside of what is needed to survive. By doing so, people will be able to eliminate their debt and then position themselves to generate wealth and use that wealth to bless other people. In addition, many adherents of Dave Ramsey's materials also use the phrase "beans and rice lifestyle" as a

metaphor for living financially frugal lives. See Dave Ramsey talk about "living like no one else" - https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Tom_PeRvgil

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Forbearance / fortitude / patience:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Diligence / self-discipline / excellence:

– Yes

Notes: Debt elimination takes lots of self-discipline and many leaders and preachers within the no-debt movement emphasize the importance of having the discipline of making and sticking to a budget to eliminate debt in the long run. See a video class from Biola University on how to make a budget - https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Lxs6cRYO-HE&feature=emb_logo

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Assertiveness / decisiveness / confidence / initiative:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Strength (physical):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Power / status / nobility:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Humility / modesty:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Contentment / serenity / equanimity:

– Yes

Notes: Contentment is key to debt elimination. Adherents are taught that they need to change their worldview on material goods, social status, and wealth. In order to start eliminating debt, adherents need to be content with where they are at and with what they have. Some adherents may have to give up what they have in order to downsize their lives in order to start paying off their debts.

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Joyfulness / enthusiasm / cheerfulness:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Optimism / hope:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Gratitude / thankfulness:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Reverence / awe / wonder:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Faith / belief / trust / devotion:

– Yes

Notes: Faith is a crucial component of evangelical culture. Pastors teach their congregants about the necessity of faith and how to use their faith to minister to others.

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Wisdom / understanding:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Discernment / intelligence:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Beauty / attractiveness:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Cleanliness (physical) / orderliness:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

↳ Other important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– Yes

Notes: Most people taking seminars or courses through Crown Financial Ministries or Ramsey Solutions identify as evangelical and hold to evangelical ethics of sexual abstinence outside of marriage.

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

Monogamy (males):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

Monogamy (females):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

Other sexual constraints (males):

– Yes

Notes: Sexual abstinence unless one is married.

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

Other sexual constraints (females):

– Yes

Notes: Sexual abstinence unless one is married.

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Notes: There is no requirement to sacrifice valuable property or items but there is an encouragement to cut up credit cards. Ramsey Solutions encourages people who are going through Financial Peace University to cut up their cards in front of the group. Often, the host of the group or the facilitator will designate for people to formally pull out their credit cards and cut them up in front of their peers. The shards of the credit cards are often collected and placed in a large container or box so the class can see how many credit cards have been cut up so far. Other groups use the credit card shards for artistic purposes such as wall art or Christmas ornaments to help remind people of being released from financial bondage.

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Notes: One of the primary sacrifices of time for no-debt ministries is attending classes and seminars. For example, Dave Ramsey's Financial Peace University (FPU) requires people to attend nine sessions of the seminar. These sessions are often held at a church or in someone's home. The material for these sessions is prepackaged and usually requires only a facilitator to manage the video and to ask discussion questions at the end of each session.

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private,

household):

– No

Notes: Although the ritual is not required for participants, numerous evangelicals that have used Dave Ramsey's materials and teachings to get out of debt make a pilgrimage to Ramsey's headquarters in Tennessee to perform the debt-free scream. Participants of the debt-free scream get to scream that they are debt-free on the air of Ramsey's radio show or they get to run through a special banner or tunnel outside while they scream to declare that they are no longer in debt. Check out this video of the debt-free scream - https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=o_8ebac0ZWc

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale "ceremonies" and "festivals."

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A state

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Yes

Notes: The no-debt movement is grounded by providing formal education through its programs, classes, seminars, and training that take place in local churches and public spaces throughout the United States. Although financial education in evangelical churches was nothing new, the Great Recession from 2007 to 2009 brought a renewed interest and resurgence of financial education within churches. Christianity Today ran a study called State of the Plate in 2010 where they gathered data regarding how pastors planned to address the financial crisis. 65% of pastors said they would use financial education courses in their churches. Furthermore, the study showed that pastors preferred the following curriculum: 1) Dave Ramsey, 58% 2) Crown Financial Ministries, 54% 3) Denominational resources, 44% 4) Brian Kluth/Maximum Generosity, 43% 5) Church Law & Tax Report, 41% 6) Your Church magazine, 35% One of the early leaders of evangelical financial education was Larry Burkett. In 1976, Burkett founded Christian Financial Concepts, an organization that focused on teaching evangelicals money management based on biblical principles. Burkett became synonymous with evangelical financial ministries during the 1980s and 1990s. His books and radio shows reached millions of people and brought about changes in the relationship between evangelical faith and financial principles. By 2000, Christian Financial Concepts merged with Crown Ministries to form Crown Financial Ministries, one of the largest evangelical financial ministries in the United States. In addition, Larry Burkett's ministry influenced numerous individuals who would later become leaders in the evangelical financial ministry world. Arguably, the most prominent evangelical no-debt leader in the United States is Dave Ramsey. He has transformed the evangelical financial landscape in the US and become the most popular financial ministry leader during and after the Great Recession. Ramsey teaches a straightforward message – get out of debt and stay out of debt. He developed and published Financial Peace University (FPU), which is a nine-week curriculum where small groups of people purchase FPU kits that come with DVDs of the teachings, workbooks, and other materials to help people learn how to get out of debt. Participants who go through the curriculum learn the practical steps to get out of debt. One of the most popular teachings from Ramsey is the debt snowball where participants list out every single debt they have from smallest to largest. They begin the snowball by tackling the smallest debt first. Once that debt is paid off, they apply the former payment to the next debt. By the time participants begin to tackle their last major form of debt, they are making large payments based on the newfound money at their disposal now that they have paid off their previous debts. Once participants are out of debt they can start to invest their money and generate wealth through cash-based living without using any form of credit. Ramsey's teachings are based on biblical texts. One of the verses that Ramsey quotes often is Proverbs 22:7, "The rich rules over the poor, And the borrower becomes the lender's slave." There is power with wealth and there is slavery with debt. Ramsey sums up this perspective in his book, Dave Ramsey's Complete Guide to Money: "Your largest wealth-building tool is your income. Over the course of your working lifetime, literally millions of dollars will pass through your hands. That's what you'll use to build wealth. It won't be lottery tickets or payday loans or American Express. Your secret weapon is your income, but if every dollar of your income goes to an endless stack of payments every month, you're literally robbing yourself of millions of dollars in future wealth. Proverbs 22:7 says it clearly, "The borrower is the slave of the lender." SLAVE. A slave can't go where he wants or do what he wants, because he is always working for somebody else. He can't make his own decisions, and he isn't free to become the person he wants to be. That's exactly what debt does to you. When you go into debt, you aren't using someone else's tools; you're submitting yourself to a new master. It doesn't get any clearer than that." Ramsey's teachings challenge people to reframe their perspective on money. Putting a person's income into the perspective of millions of dollars over a lifetime is an effort to change how people think about their ability to generate wealth. Individuals have the power to not only generate wealth but also to control more aspects of their life. Ramsey argues that debt is the opposite of power and contends that debt is equivalent to slavery. A person in debt is a financial slave who has little to no power over their lives and must submit to their "new master." Ramsey's teachings also challenge the consumer culture in the US where people go into

debt in order to purchase things they cannot afford or to live a lifestyle that is beyond their means. One of his favorite mottos is: "If you will live like no one else, later you can live like no one else.' If you make some sacrifices, inject some discipline, and get intentional about winning with money, the future is wide open. You'll be blown away at the opportunities you'll have to serve and bless other people, and you'll be amazed at what life feels like without worrying about money all the time." Ramsey's books and his curriculum at Financial Peace University reinforce the idea of living significantly below one's means in order to pay off debt quickly. Living below one's means is called living a "beans and rice" lifestyle where a person eats simple meals and only makes necessary purchases. When a person lives this way, they can use their income to get out of debt and thus get out of financial slavery.

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Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

Is formal education restricted to religious professionals:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

Is such education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Although evangelical no-debt education is primarily used by churches and other religious organizations, there are also non-religious companies and individuals who use curricula from Crown Financial Ministries or Dave Ramsey.

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: There are people in the no-debt evangelical movement that serve in the US armed forces.

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Evangelicals use the Gregorian Calendar

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: USA

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